

Supporting Information:

**Second harmonic response of azobenzene
self-assembled monolayers: the effect of
push/pull substitution**

Angela Dellai,^{*,†} Luca Muccioli,^{*,‡} Frédéric Castet,^{*,†} and Claire Tonnelé^{*,¶,§}

[†]*Univ. Bordeaux, CNRS, Bordeaux INP, Institut des Sciences Moléculaires, UMR 5255,
F-33400 Talence, France*

[‡]*Department of Industrial Chemistry, University of Bologna, 40136 Bologna, Italy;*

[¶]*Donostia International Physics Center, 20018 Donostia, Euskadi, Spain*

[§]*IKERBASQUE - Basque Foundation for Science, 48009 Bilbo, Euskadi, Spain*

E-mail: angela.dellai@u-bordeaux.fr; luca.muccioli@unibo.it; frederic.castet@u-bordeaux.fr;

claire.tonnele@dipc.org

Contents

1	Parametrization of the Force Field	S-3
1.1	Reference DFT parameters	S-3
1.2	Need to derive a new force field with respect to Ref. S1	S-7
1.3	Iterative parametrization of the bond distances and dihedrals	S-8
1.4	Assessment of the quality of the modified Force Field	S-14
2	Absorption properties of the AZO-A and AZO-D molecules	S-17
3	Structural analysis of the SAMs	S-18
4	Computation of the NLO responses	S-20
4.1	Choice of the relevant fragment for the NLO calculations	S-20
4.2	Effect of the replacement of the Si atom with a H atom when removing the anchoring group	S-22
4.3	Influence of the 5% of (E) residues in AZO-(Z) SAMs	S-23
4.4	Static NLO responses of the SAMs	S-24
4.5	Structure-property relationships	S-24
4.6	Effects of intermolecular electrostatic interactions	S-29
	References	S-29

1 Parametrization of the Force Field

1.1 Reference DFT parameters

Table S1: Isomerization energy (ΔG_{EZ} in kcal/mol), molecular dipole moment (μ , in Debye), bond length alternation along the azo bridge ($BLA = (d_{CN} + d_{NC})/2 - d_{NN}$, with d_{ij} the bond distance between atoms i and j) and torsional dihedral angles (θ_{1-5} and θ_{azo} in degrees) computed at the M06/6-311G(d) level for the full AZO-A and AZO-D molecules in their E and Z states.

Properties	AZO-A(E)	AZO-A(Z)	AZO-D(E)	AZO-D(Z)
ΔG_{EZ}	14.14		14.38	
μ	9.146	6.332	0.951	6.499
BLA	0.155	0.179	0.153	0.183
θ_1	180	179	180	179
θ_2	0	-1	0	1
θ_3	0	152	0	141
θ_{azo}	180	-10	180	-10
θ_4	0	129	0	146
θ_5	0	-1	22	22

Table S2: Isomerization energy (ΔG_{EZ} in kcal/mol), molecular dipole moment (μ , in Debye), bond length alternation (in Å) along the azo bridge ($BLA = (d_{CN} + d_{NC})/2 - d_{NN}$, with d_{ij} the bond distance between atoms i and j) and torsional dihedral angles (θ_{1-5} and θ_{azo} in degrees) computed at the M06/6-311G(d) level for the AZO-A and AZO-D molecular fragments after truncation of the alkyl chain.

Properties	AZO-A(E)	AZO-A(Z)	AZO-D(E)	AZO-D(Z)
ΔG_{EZ}	14.49		15.55	
μ	8.269	6.379	1.926	4.923
BLA	0.155	0.179	0.153	0.182
θ_1	180	180	180	180
θ_2	0	0	0	0
θ_3	0	151	0	139
θ_{azo}	180	-10	180	-10
θ_4	0	130	0	147
θ_5	0	-1	23	22

Figure S1: Atom numbering and specific atom labeling adopted during the parameterization of *trans* and *cis* isomers of AZO-A and AZO-D compounds. The same atom labels are considered in the analogous fragments.

Table S3: Electrostatic potential charges (ESP) as computed at the M06/6-311g(d) level and averaged among chemical equivalency. Note that one hydrogen atom (H3) has been removed and its charge added to the neighboring oxygen atom (O2). See Figure S1 for atom numbers and types.

Atom	AZO-A(E)	AZO-A(Z)	AZO-D(E)	AZO-D(Z)
Si1	si 1.35137	si 1.34342	si 1.3665	si 1.2726
O2	oi -0.39219	oi -0.38718	oi -0.3948	oih -0.3729
O4	oh -0.88418	oh -0.87792	oh -0.8866	oh -0.8657
H5	ho 0.49199	ho 0.49074	ho 0.4918	ho 0.4928
O6	oh -0.88418	oh -0.87792	oh -0.8866	oh -0.8657
H7	ho 0.49199	ho 0.49074	ho 0.4918	ho 0.4928
C8	c3 -0.36985	c3 -0.43123	c3 -0.4041	c3 -0.3483
H9	hc 0.07529	hc 0.09331	hc 0.0837	hc 0.0749

Continuation of Table S3

Atom	AZO-A(E)		AZO-A(Z)		AZO-D(E)		AZO-D(Z)	
H10	hc	0.07529	hc	0.09331	hc	0.0837	hc	0.0749
C11	c3	0.06058	c3	0.10342	c3	0.1057	c3	0.0858
H12	hc	-0.01877	hc	-0.02263	hc	-0.0279	hc	-0.0218
H13	hc	-0.01877	hc	-0.02263	hc	-0.0279	hc	-0.0218
C14	c3	0.09615	c3	0.04786	c3	0.0104	c3	0.0424
H15	hc	-0.02144	hc	-0.01119	hc	-0.0057	hc	-0.0123
H16	hc	-0.02144	hc	-0.01119	hc	-0.0057	hc	-0.0123
C17	c3	-0.07555	c3	-0.04292	c3	0.0606	c3	-0.0496
H18	hc	0.00861	hc	0.00567	hc	-0.0167	hc	0.0053
H19	hc	0.00861	hc	0.00567	hc	-0.0167	hc	0.0053
C20	c3	0.11732	c3	0.05535	c3	-0.0364	c3	0.1104
H21	hc	-0.02969	hc	-0.01365	hc	-0.0013	hc	-0.0260
H22	hc	-0.02969	hc	-0.01365	hc	-0.0013	hc	-0.0260
C23	c3	-0.04323	c3	-0.01222	c3	0.0867	c3	-0.0678
H24	hc	0.00021	hc	-0.00124	hc	-0.0259	hc	0.0057
H25	hc	0.00021	hc	-0.00124	hc	-0.0259	hc	0.0057
C26	c3	0.05367	c3	-0.00701	c3	-0.0427	c3	0.0730
H27	hc	-0.01634	hc	-0.00171	hc	-0.0004	hc	-0.0199
H28	hc	-0.01634	hc	-0.00171	hc	-0.0004	hc	-0.0199
C29	c3	0.03408	c3	0.09076	c3	0.1694	c3	0.0277
H30	hc	-0.00930	hc	-0.01556	hc	-0.0393	hc	-0.0079
H31	hc	-0.00930	hc	-0.01556	hc	-0.0393	hc	-0.0079
C32	c3	0.04563	c3	-0.04941	c3	-0.0952	c3	0.0189
H33	hc	-0.01819	hc	0.00410	hc	0.0080	hc	-0.0102
H34	hc	-0.01819	hc	0.00410	hc	0.0080	hc	-0.0102
C35	c3	-0.12276	c3	-0.07141	c3	-0.0046	c3	-0.1222
H36	hc	0.03988	hc	0.03369	hc	0.0210	hc	0.0421
H37	hc	0.03988	hc	0.03369	hc	0.0210	hc	0.0421
C38	c3	0.37887	c3	0.35095	c3	0.2719	c3	0.3851
H39	hc	-0.02705	hc	-0.02726	hc	-0.0056	hc	-0.0344
H40	hc	-0.02705	hc	-0.02726	hc	-0.0056	hc	-0.0344
O41	os	-0.41758	os	-0.41790	os	-0.4214	os	-0.4392
C42	ce	0.43773	cy	0.45192	ce	0.4547	cy	0.4196
C43	ca	-0.35337	cb	-0.30768	ce	-0.3614	cy	-0.2861
C44	cg	-0.35337	cz	-0.30768	cg	-0.3614	cz	-0.2861
C45	ca	-0.06900	cb	-0.28170	ce	-0.0693	cy	-0.3239

Continuation of Table S3

Atom	AZO-A(E)		AZO-A(Z)		AZO-D(E)		AZO-D(Z)	
C46	cg	-0.06900	cz	-0.28170	cg	-0.0693	cz	-0.3239
H47	ha	0.17944	ha	0.17674	ha	0.1707	ha	0.1623
H48	ha	0.17944	ha	0.17674	ha	0.1707	ha	0.1623
H49	ha	0.10824	ha	0.19303	ha	0.1047	ha	0.2118
H50	ha	0.10824	ha	0.19303	ha	0.1047	ha	0.2118
C51	ce	0.22034	cy	0.43802	ce	0.1863	cy	0.4829
N52	nf	-0.19276	n2	-0.23372	nf	-0.1999	n2	-0.3054
N53	ne	-0.25197	n1	-0.37408	ne	-0.2548	n1	-0.3335
C54	ce	0.36798	cy	0.77243	ca	0.3172	cb	0.6266
C55	cg	-0.15380	cb	-0.49859	cg	-0.1274	cz	-0.4106
C56	ca	-0.15380	cb	-0.49859	cg	-0.1274	cz	-0.4106
C57	cg	-0.15619	cb	-0.05575	cg	-0.3197	cz	-0.2572
C58	ca	-0.15619	cb	-0.05575	cg	-0.3197	cz	-0.2572
H59	ha	0.10821	ha	0.24045	ha	0.0998	ha	0.2164
H60	ha	0.10821	ha	0.24045	ha	0.0998	ha	0.2164
H61	ha	0.18172	ha	0.16624	ha	0.1884	ha	0.1794
H62	ha	0.18172	ha	0.16624	ha	0.1884	ha	0.1794
C63	ca	-0.09345	cz	-0.10786	ce	0.3264	cy	0.3530
N64	no	0.81337	no	0.77434	nh	-0.7610	nh	-0.8124
O65/H65	o	-0.44516	o	-0.43588	hn	0.3485	hn	0.3619
O66/H66	o	-0.44516	o	-0.43588	hn	0.3485	hn	0.3619

1.2 Need to derive a new force field with respect to Ref. S1

The reparametrization of torsional potentials focused on six dihedral angles ($\theta_1 - \theta_5$ and θ_{azo}), as shown in the insert Figures of Tables S1 and S2. Before embarking on laborious parameterization work, we checked the possibility of using the same Force Field (FF) for θ_{1-4} as the one developed in Ref. S1 for the *trans* and *cis* AZO-H isomers. As shown in Figure S2 for both isomers of AZO-A, the differences in the reference DFT energy profiles and the one obtained by the FF of Ref. S1 are large, excluding the possibility to transfer the dihedrals parametrized for the non-substitued systems. A specific FF parametrization is therefore necessary for the AZO-R systems. Note that for θ_1 , that is the dihedral which is the most

far away from the R group, the FF developed in Ref. S1 for the non-substituted azobenzene derivative is able to reproduce the profile computed at DFT. However, this dihedral was also reparameterized together with the other dihedrals.

Figure S2: Comparison between the torsional energy profiles around the $\theta_1 - \theta_4$ dihedrals obtained with DFT (dots) at the M06/6-311G(d) level and with the parametrized force field (continuous line) used in Ref. S1.

1.3 Iterative parametrization of the bond distances and dihedrals

The strategy adopted in the FF parametrization is as follows: firstly, we carried out the parametrization of bond lengths with respect to the reference DFT values, starting with the `gaff2` parameters for both bonds, angles and dihedrals. Next, we tuned the bond distances paying attention in adjusting the C-C and N-C bonds to reproduce the bond length alternation (BLA) along the azo bridge computed at the DFT level. Once we reached a value of the mean-absolute error (MAE) below an arbitrary threshold value of 0.01 Å for bond distances, we carried out the parameterization of the dihedrals using the `NAMD` code and the `CHARMM` force field on the molecular fragments with truncated alkyl chain (insert Figure of Table S2). Then, we checked that the force field is transferable to the full system (insert Figure of Table S1). Lastly, the bond distances have been retuned to minimize the error with respect to DFT, with particular attention on the bond lengths that are expected to affect the NLO responses of the systems, namely those of the conjugated azobenzene core. At every step of the parametrization procedure, the MAE on the bond distances, on the BLA, as well

on the NLO properties (namely on the HRS responses β_{HRS} and DR) were calculated with respect to the corresponding values simulated from the DFT equilibrium geometries.

In Figures S3, S4, S5 and S6 the torsional profiles around the θ_{1-5} dihedrals computed at the DFT level (black dots) and using the reparametrized FF (continuous lines) are reported for the investigated systems. The torsional profiles around θ_{azo} are also reported for E isomers in both the ground S_0 and first excited S_1 state, parametrized with respect to CASPT2 reference calculations (gray dots).^{S2} In all plots, the torsional profiles parametrized for the fragments with truncated alkyl chain (orange line), the one obtained by transferring the parameters to the full systems (green line), and the ones simulated after re-tuning the bond lengths, that is the final one (blue line), are illustrated.

Figure S3: QM torsional energy profiles of AZO-A(E) (dots), calculated at the M06/6-311G(d) level for $\theta_1 - \theta_5$ and at the CASPT2 level for θ_{azo} in both the ground (S_0) and excited states (S_1), compared with profiles calculated with the reparametrized force field (continuous lines), where the orange line refers to the torsional profile of the fragment with truncated alkyl chains, the green line to the full system, and the blue one to the final force field chosen for the MD simulations.

Figure S4: QM torsional energy profiles of AZO-A(Z) (dots) calculated at the M06/6-311G(d) level for $\theta_1 - \theta_5$, compared with profiles calculated with the reparametrized force field (continuous lines), where the orange line refers to the torsional profile of the fragment with truncated alkyl chains, the green line to the full system, and the blue one to the final force field chosen for the MD simulations.

Figure S5: QM torsional energy profiles of AZO-D(E) (dots), calculated at the M06/6-311G(d) level for $\theta_1 - \theta_5$ and at the CASPT2 level for θ_{azo} in both the ground (S_0) and excited states (S_1), compared with profiles calculated with the reparametrized force field (continuous lines), where the orange line refers to the torsional profile of the fragment with truncated alkyl chains, the green line to the full system, and the blue one to the final force field chosen for the MD simulations.

Figure S6: QM torsional energy profiles of AZO-D(Z) (dots) calculated at the M06/6-311G(d) level for $\theta_1 - \theta_5$, compared with profiles calculated with the reparametrized force field (continuous lines), where the orange line refers to the torsional profile of the fragment with truncated alkyl chains, the green line to the full system, and the blue one to the final force field chosen for the MD simulations.

1.4 Assessment of the quality of the modified Force Field

Table S4: Bond length alternation along the azo bridge (BLA, in Å) and static hyperpolarizability ($\beta(0;0,0)$, in a.u.) of *trans* AZO-A and AZO-E isomers, computed using the DFT geometry, using the geometry optimized with the original GAFF force field, and using the force field (FF) derived in this work. Deviations (in %) with respect to values computed using the DFT geometry are listed in the last column.

Compound	Property	DFT	GAFF	FF	% GAFF	% FF
AZO-A(E)	BLA	0.1545	0.0885	0.1540	-43	-0.3
	$\beta(0;0,0)$	8448	2334	9283	-72	10
AZO-D(E)	BLA	0.1530	0.0908	0.1536	-41	0.4
	$\beta(0;0,0)$	799	122	690	-85	-14

Table S5: Bond distances of the four investigated systems, as computed at the M06/6-311G(d) level and with the parameterized Force Field. Deviations (in %) are listed in the last column. Mean absolute errors (MAE) are reported in Table S6.

Atom label	AZO-A(E)			AZO-A(Z)			AZO-D(E)			AZO-D(Z)		
	QM	FF	var%									
Si1 O2	1.642	1.723	0.081	1.640	1.721	0.081	1.640	1.721	0.081	1.640	1.722	0.082
Si1 O4	1.653	1.690	0.037	1.652	1.692	0.040	1.643	1.685	0.042	1.652	1.696	0.043
Si1 O6	1.640	1.689	0.049	1.643	1.686	0.043	1.653	1.692	0.039	1.643	1.689	0.046
Si1 C8	1.852	1.890	0.038	1.852	1.885	0.033	1.851	1.887	0.035	1.852	1.892	0.040
O4 H5	0.957	0.965	0.008	0.957	0.966	0.009	0.958	0.967	0.008	0.957	0.966	0.009
O6 H7	0.958	0.967	0.009	0.958	0.966	0.008	0.957	0.966	0.009	0.958	0.966	0.008
C8 H9	1.099	1.097	0.002	1.100	1.098	0.002	1.101	1.097	0.004	1.101	1.096	0.005
C8 H10	1.101	1.097	0.004	1.101	1.096	0.005	1.100	1.097	0.003	1.099	1.098	0.002
C8 C11	1.525	1.517	0.008	1.525	1.517	0.008	1.524	1.516	0.008	1.525	1.518	0.007
C11 H12	1.101	1.099	0.002	1.101	1.099	0.002	1.102	1.098	0.004	1.102	1.099	0.003
C11 H13	1.101	1.099	0.002	1.102	1.099	0.003	1.101	1.098	0.003	1.102	1.098	0.004
C11 C14	1.518	1.522	0.004	1.519	1.521	0.002	1.518	1.521	0.003	1.518	1.522	0.004
C14 H15	1.102	1.099	0.003	1.103	1.101	0.002	1.102	1.100	0.003	1.103	1.100	0.003
C14 H16	1.102	1.100	0.002	1.102	1.100	0.002	1.103	1.099	0.004	1.101	1.100	0.002
C14 C17	1.518	1.522	0.004	1.517	1.521	0.004	1.516	1.521	0.005	1.517	1.522	0.004
C17 H18	1.102	1.099	0.003	1.102	1.100	0.002	1.103	1.100	0.003	1.102	1.099	0.003
C17 H19	1.102	1.100	0.002	1.103	1.099	0.004	1.102	1.099	0.003	1.103	1.099	0.003
C17 C20	1.517	1.521	0.004	1.518	1.521	0.003	1.518	1.521	0.003	1.517	1.521	0.004
C20 H21	1.102	1.100	0.002	1.103	1.100	0.003	1.102	1.099	0.003	1.102	1.100	0.002
C20 H22	1.102	1.099	0.003	1.102	1.099	0.003	1.102	1.100	0.002	1.102	1.099	0.003
C20 C23	1.517	1.520	0.003	1.516	1.522	0.006	1.517	1.521	0.004	1.517	1.521	0.003
C23 H24	1.102	1.099	0.003	1.102	1.099	0.003	1.102	1.099	0.003	1.102	1.099	0.003

Continuation of Table S3

Atom label	AZO-A(E)			AZO-A(Z)			AZO-D(E)			AZO-D(Z)		
C23 H25	1.102	1.100	0.002	1.103	1.099	0.004	1.102	1.099	0.003	1.103	1.100	0.003
C23 C26	1.517	1.521	0.004	1.518	1.522	0.004	1.517	1.521	0.004	1.516	1.521	0.005
C26 H27	1.103	1.100	0.003	1.102	1.100	0.002	1.102	1.100	0.002	1.102	1.100	0.002
C26 H28	1.103	1.099	0.004	1.101	1.100	0.001	1.102	1.099	0.003	1.102	1.100	0.002
C26 C29	1.517	1.521	0.004	1.517	1.521	0.004	1.517	1.521	0.003	1.517	1.521	0.004
C29 H30	1.102	1.100	0.002	1.102	1.099	0.003	1.101	1.099	0.002	1.102	1.100	0.002
C29 H31	1.102	1.099	0.003	1.101	1.099	0.002	1.103	1.099	0.004	1.102	1.099	0.003
C29 C32	1.517	1.521	0.004	1.517	1.521	0.004	1.517	1.522	0.005	1.517	1.521	0.004
C32 H33	1.101	1.099	0.002	1.102	1.100	0.002	1.102	1.100	0.002	1.102	1.100	0.003
C32 H34	1.102	1.100	0.002	1.102	1.100	0.002	1.103	1.100	0.003	1.103	1.099	0.004
C32 C35	1.518	1.520	0.002	1.518	1.522	0.004	1.516	1.522	0.005	1.517	1.521	0.004
C35 H36	1.099	1.099	0.000	1.099	1.100	0.001	1.099	1.099	0.000	1.099	1.099	0.000
C35 H37	1.099	1.099	0.000	1.100	1.100	0.000	1.100	1.099	0.000	1.100	1.099	0.000
C35 C38	1.506	1.515	0.009	1.506	1.517	0.011	1.506	1.518	0.011	1.506	1.516	0.010
C38 H39	1.102	1.099	0.003	1.103	1.099	0.004	1.103	1.099	0.004	1.103	1.100	0.004
C38 H40	1.102	1.099	0.003	1.102	1.099	0.003	1.103	1.099	0.004	1.103	1.100	0.003
C38 O41	1.417	1.416	0.001	1.417	1.416	0.001	1.412	1.419	0.008	1.412	1.416	0.004
O41 C42	1.342	1.342	0.000	1.343	1.344	0.001	1.349	1.345	0.004	1.351	1.345	0.006
C42 C43	1.395	1.393	0.002	1.394	1.395	0.001	1.393	1.387	0.006	1.392	1.389	0.002
C42 C44	1.403	1.394	0.009	1.400	1.397	0.003	1.401	1.394	0.007	1.398	1.395	0.003
C43 C45	1.385	1.380	0.005	1.385	1.385	0.000	1.387	1.390	0.003	1.389	1.393	0.004
C43 H47	1.085	1.084	0.001	1.086	1.085	0.001	1.085	1.083	0.002	1.086	1.085	0.001
C44 C46	1.371	1.377	0.006	1.374	1.380	0.006	1.373	1.377	0.004	1.377	1.380	0.004
C44 H48	1.087	1.086	0.001	1.087	1.087	0.000	1.087	1.086	0.002	1.087	1.087	0.000
C45 H49	1.087	1.087	0.000	1.087	1.088	0.001	1.087	1.088	0.001	1.087	1.087	0.001
C45 C51	1.392	1.395	0.003	1.391	1.394	0.003	1.389	1.389	0.000	1.388	1.385	0.002
C46 H50	1.085	1.087	0.002	1.086	1.085	0.001	1.086	1.087	0.001	1.088	1.086	0.002
C46 C51	1.403	1.410	0.007	1.401	1.409	0.008	1.401	1.414	0.013	1.399	1.405	0.007
C51 N52	1.399	1.398	0.001	1.421	1.443	0.022	1.407	1.407	0.000	1.426	1.426	0.000
N52 N53	1.251	1.251	0.000	1.240	1.241	0.001	1.252	1.252	0.000	1.242	1.241	0.001
N53 C54	1.412	1.412	0.000	1.418	1.428	0.010	1.402	1.404	0.002	1.423	1.420	0.003
C54 C55	1.397	1.405	0.008	1.395	1.383	0.012	1.399	1.400	0.001	1.393	1.389	0.003
C54 C56	1.395	1.390	0.005	1.396	1.385	0.011	1.394	1.393	0.001	1.397	1.395	0.002
C55 C57	1.379	1.376	0.003	1.381	1.380	0.001	1.375	1.379	0.003	1.380	1.382	0.001
C55 H59	1.086	1.086	0.000	1.087	1.085	0.002	1.086	1.087	0.001	1.088	1.085	0.002
C56 C58	1.382	1.378	0.004	1.380	1.378	0.002	1.380	1.379	0.002	1.379	1.381	0.002
C56 H60	1.087	1.087	0.000	1.088	1.085	0.003	1.088	1.087	0.001	1.087	1.084	0.003
C57 H61	1.085	1.091	0.006	1.085	1.091	0.006	1.090	1.085	0.006	1.088	1.086	0.002
C57 C63	1.390	1.389	0.001	1.387	1.388	0.001	1.405	1.392	0.012	1.399	1.393	0.006

Continuation of Table S3

Atom label	AZO-A(E)			AZO-A(Z)			AZO-D(E)			AZO-D(Z)		
C58 H62	1.085	1.091	0.006	1.085	1.091	0.006	1.089	1.086	0.003	1.089	1.087	0.002
C58 C63	1.385	1.387	0.002	1.387	1.387	0.000	1.398	1.393	0.005	1.401	1.393	0.007
C63 N64	1.474	1.474	0.000	1.470	1.470	0.000	1.379	1.378	0.001	1.381	1.383	0.001
N64 O65/H65	1.213	1.214	0.001	1.214	1.213	0.001	1.010	1.009	0.000	1.010	1.010	0.000
N64 O66/H66	1.213	1.214	0.001	1.213	1.214	0.001	1.009	1.010	0.001	1.010	1.010	0.000

Figure S7: Superimposition of the equilibrium geometries optimized at the DFT level and using the parameterized FF. The root-mean-square deviations (RMSD) of atomic positions (*rmsd*) are reported in Table S6.

Table S6: Structural and NLO properties calculated from geometries optimized with DFT and with the parametrized FF. The Table reports the BLA (in Å), the θ_{1-5} and θ_{azo} dihedrals (in degrees), the mean absolute errors on the bond lengths including or not the terminal -Si(OH)₂ group (MAE and MAE', respectively), the root-mean-square deviations of atomic positions (RMSD in Å, calculated with the *Chimera* program), and the static and dynamic ($\lambda_{inc} = 800$ nm) HRS first hyperpolarizabilities (β_{HRS} , in a.u.) and depolarization ratios (DR , dimensionless). Standard deviations are reported in parentheses.

	AZO-A(E)		AZO-A(Z)		AZO-D(E)		AZO-D(Z)	
	DFT	FF	DFT	FF	DFT	FF	DFT	FF
BLA	0.1545	0.1540 (-0.3%)	0.1795	0.1945(+8.4%)	0.1530	0.1536 (+0.4%)	0.1825	0.1817 (-0.4%)
θ_1	180	180	179	180	180	180	179	180
θ_2	0	1	-1	-1	0	0	1	0
θ_3	0	0	152	151	0	-1	141	144
θ_{azo}	180	177	-10	-13	180	180	-10	-11
θ_4	0	0	129	133	0	-1	146	148
θ_5	0	0	-1	-1	22	21	22	21
MAE	/	0.006	/	0.006	/	0.006	/	0.006
MAE'	/	0.003	/	0.004	/	0.003	/	0.0003
rmsd	/	0.134	/	0.184	/	0.109	/	0.153
Static β_{HRS}	3551	3901 (+10%)	1120	1176 (+5%)	354	299 (-15%)	675	759 (+12%)
Static DR	4.75	4.76 (+0.32%)	6.29	6.24 (-1%)	4.22	4.34 (+2.74%)	3.30	3.26 (-1.17%)
Dynamic β_{HRS}	19419	21337 (+10%)	3280	3763 (+15%)	2431	1864 (-23%)	1622	2003 (+23%)
Dynamic DR	4.98	4.98 (0.00%)	6.66	6.58 (-1%)	4.84	4.83 (-0.24%)	2.99	2.99 (+0.03%)

2 Absorption properties of the AZO-A and AZO-D molecules

Figure S8: Simulated absorption spectra of AZO-A(E), AZO-A(Z), AZO-D(E) and AZO-D(Z) computed at the M06-2X/6-311+G(d) level using their DFT-optimized geometries.

3 Structural analysis of the SAMs

To validate the decision to limit the analysis to 1000 frames, we compared the one-dimensional radial distribution function (1D RDF) and tilt angle distribution of the AZO-A(E) segment computed from 1000 structures against those derived from all 100000 configurations saved during the production run of the simulation (Figure S9). The results in both cases are nearly identical, confirming that this selected subset of snapshots is representative of the dynamics of the systems.

Figure S9: 1D density of neighbors of AZO-A(E) (left) and distribution of the tilt angle (θ) calculated with 1000 (in red) and 100000 (in black) snapshots extracted from the MD trajectories.

Figure S10: Two-dimensional density of neighbors ($N(x, y)$) for the azobenzene moieties (top) and of the alkyl chain (bottom) in the AZO-A and AZO-D SAMs in their respective *trans* and *cis* conformations.

Further analyses of the conformations adopted by the photoswitchable AZO units within the SAMs are reported below, focusing on the values adopted by the flexible torsional angles (θ_{1-5}). Figure S11 shows the probability distribution of these angles for the set of geometries extracted from the MD trajectories, plotted versus the torsional potential of the DFT-optimized molecule. These plots evidence that the majority of the conformers stay in the minima of the torsional potentials. However, despite the symmetrical shape of the energy potentials, some torsion angle distributions have a slightly asymmetrical shape, like θ_1 in all the four systems (probably because of the uniform tilt of the alkyl chains), θ_3 in the *cis*-isomers, and θ_5 in the NH_2 -substituted systems.

Figure S11: Probability distribution (in pink) of dihedrals θ_{1-5} in the *trans* and *cis* forms of AZO-A and AZO-D (as well as of θ_{az0} for *trans* configurations), plotted versus the torsional potentials (in blue).

4 Computation of the NLO responses

4.1 Choice of the relevant fragment for the NLO calculations

A benchmark study was performed in Ref. S1 for the AZO-H system in order to define the relevant molecular fragments that must be considered for the NLO calculations, i.e., the truncation offering the best compromise between accuracy and computational cost. It was concluded that, in addition to the AZO core, the $-(\text{CH}_2)_{10}\text{CH}_3$ alkyl chain has to be explicitly included, while the $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_2\text{O}-$ anchoring group can be omitted. Here, we further

validate the choice of such truncation for the AZO-A and AZO-D molecules, by considering the different structures illustrated in Figure S12: (1) the reference full molecule, (2) the molecule in which the alkyl chain is truncated to $(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{-CH}_3$, and (3) the molecule in which the $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_2\text{O-}$ anchoring group is removed. The static and dynamic β values calculated for the different structures with $\text{R}=\text{NO}_2/\text{NH}_2$ are reported in Table S7 and S8.

As it was concluded in Ref. S1 for AZO-H, the anchoring group can be removed in the NLO calculations, as its presence affects only slightly the β response. On the contrary, truncating the alkyl chain significantly modifies the response of all the investigated systems. Hence, the molecular fragment employed for the NLO calculations is AZO(3).

Figure S12: Different structures considered for defining the most relevant molecular truncation for the NLO calculations.

Table S7: Static and dynamic first hyperpolarizability (β , in a.u.) of the *trans* and *cis* isomers of AZO-A, computed at the M06-2X/6-311+G(d) level, using the different AZO(1), AZO(2) and AZO(3) structures shown in Figure S12. The variations (in %) are reported with respect to the values computed for AZO(1).

Type	AZO-A(E)					AZO-A(Z)				
	(1)	(2)	var%	(3)	var%	(1)	(2)	var%	(3)	var%
$\lambda_{inc} = \infty$										
β	8448	7652	-9	8497	1	2869	2629	-8	2904	1
$\lambda_{inc} = 800 \text{ nm}$										
β	46769	41512	-11	46956	0.4	8434	7712	-9	8457	0.3

Table S8: Static and dynamic first hyperpolarizability (β , in a.u.) of the *trans* and *cis* isomers of AZO-D, computed at the M06-2X/6-311+G(d) level, using the different AZO(1), AZO(2) and AZO(3) structures shown in Figure S12. The variations (in %) are reported with respect to the values computed for AZO(1).

Type	AZO-D(E)					AZO-D(Z)				
	(1)	(2)	var%	(3)	var%	(1)	(2)	var%	(3)	var%
$\lambda_{inc} = \infty$										
β	799	958	20	723	-10	1382	1364	-1	1427	3
$\lambda_{inc} = 800$ nm										
β	5741	6386	11	5617	-2	3228	3237	0.3	3279	2

4.2 Effect of the replacement of the Si atom with a H atom when removing the anchoring group

As described in the methodological section, the NLO calculations were carried out on a total of 610 structural snapshots extracted from the MD trajectories of each SAM. As discussed above, the Si(OH)₂O- anchoring group was removed, and the Si atom was replaced by a hydrogen atom to complete the valence of the terminal carbon. For convenience, this hydrogen atom was placed at the position of the silicon without further optimization. As a consequence, the corresponding C-H bond is much longer (between 1.797 and 1.990 Å) than the optimal chemical bond between carbon and hydrogen. To validate the fact that the presence of this elongated C-H bond in the terminal methyl group does not introduce large deviations in the NLO responses, we performed test calculations on AZO-A(E) as a representative example. In Table S9, we report the NLO response of three MD structural frames implying elongated C-H bonds. Frames 1-3 were selected because the C-H distance in these structures respectively corresponds to the minimal, average, and maximal value of the C-Si bond lengths spanned during the dynamics (see Figure S13). The NLO response of these three structures is compared in Table S9 with the NLO response calculated for the same molecular geometry, in which the C-H bond has been adjusted to its optimal length (1.07 Å). The overall small deviations of β between structures implying elongated and optimized C-H bonds validate the use of the molecular fragments built upon the brutal substitution of

the silicon atom with the hydrogen atom.

Figure S13: Molecular structures of AZO-A(E) with optimized (a) and elongated (b) C-H bonds. The minimum, averaged and maximum values of the C-Si bond (becoming the elongated C-H bond) within the 610 structural snapshots extracted from the SAM are reported on the right.

Table S9: Static and dynamic NLO properties of three selected frames of AZO-A(E) extracted from the MD simulations, with the optimal (a) and elongated (b) C-H bond. *var%* is the difference between the two structures.

		$\lambda_{inc} = \infty$			$\lambda_{inc} = 800 \text{ nm}$		
		frame1	frame2	frame3	frame1	frame2	frame3
β	a	7584	9711	8663	44095	62011	49817
	b	6918	9078	8276	42717	60459	48960
<i>var%</i>		-10	-7	-5	-3	-3	-2

4.3 Influence of the 5% of (E) residues in AZO-(Z) SAMs

The statistical averages of the NLO responses of AZO-A(Z) and AZO-D(Z) reported in the main text include the few residues that did not photoswitch, i.e. the 5% remaining in (E)-form (see Figure 2b). The effect of the presence of these residual non-switched AZO units can be seen in Figure S14, where we compare the β distributions of two different molecular ensembles, including: i) all the residues of the AZO-A(Z) and AZO-D(Z) monolayers, so both the 95% of the fragments in (Z)-form and the 5% in (E)-form, and ii) only the fragments in the (Z) form. For AZO-D, no significant difference is noted when comparing the distributions obtained for the two ensembles, due to the small β variation from the *trans* to *cis* form.

On the contrary, the presence of non-switched (E)-residues in AZO-A slightly increases the average β value.

Figure S14: Comparison of the distribution of static β values in the *cis* AZO-A and AZO-D SAMs statistically averaged between all residues (i.e. containing 3 non-photoswitched residues that are still in the *trans* form), labeled *all*, and the one with only the fragments which photoisomerized, labeled *only(Z)*.

4.4 Static NLO responses of the SAMs

Figure S15: Distributions of the static β , β_z and a_β values in the different monolayers, obtained without electrostatic embedding. Average values and standard deviations are also reported.

4.5 Structure-property relationships

To gain a deeper understanding of the link between the geometrical structures of the AZO residues and the NLO properties of the SAMs, we first explored possible correlations between

molecular first hyperpolarizabilities and some electronic or geometrical parameters. The evolution of the static and frequency-dependent β responses as a function of the bond length alternation (BLA) along the azo bridge and of the torsional angles (θ_1 - θ_5 and θ_{azo} , defined in Figure 1b) are shown in Figures S16 and S17. Although no clear correlation is observed with any of the parameters, the β values of the *trans* isomers seem to be more affected by the changes in BLA compared to *cis* isomers, particularly for AZO-A.

Figure S16: Correlation between the norm of the static (top) and dynamic ($\lambda_{inc} = 800$ nm) (bottom) first hyperpolarizability (β in a.u.) and the bond length alternation (BLA in \AA) for AZO-A and AZO-D in the *trans* and *cis* forms. Dotted lines show the values calculated for the equilibrium DFT geometries.

Figure S17: Scatter plots of the norm of the static (top) and dynamic ($\lambda_{inc} = 800$ nm) (bottom) first hyperpolarizability (β in a.u.) and the torsional angles (θ_i in degrees) for AZO-A and AZO-D in the *trans* and *cis* forms.

Secondly, we investigated how the interfacial NLO response perpendicular to the surface (β_z) is connected to the tilt of the photoswitches within the SAMs. The correlation of the static values of β_z with the previously defined tilt angles θ_{AZO} , θ_{Ph1} and θ_{Ph2} are illustrated in Figures S18 and S19. As one might intuitively expect, the more the photoswitches are aligned vertically along the z -direction ($\theta_{AZO} \rightarrow 0$), the larger β_z should be. This is indeed the behavior observed for AZO-A(E) (and in a less pronounced fashion for AZO-A(Z)). Contrarily, no clear correlation between the tilt θ_{AZO} and β_z is remarked in the AZO-D(E) SAM. Interestingly, a quite marked correlation between β_z and the orientation of the two phenyl rings (characterized by the θ_{Ph1} and θ_{Ph2} tilt angles) is observed in AZO-D(Z).

Figure S18: Scatter plots of the z -component of the static first hyperpolarizability (β_z in a.u.) and the tilt angles characterizing the orientation of the AZO units within the SAMs (θ_{AZO} , θ_{Ph1} and θ_{Ph2} , in degrees).

Figure S19: Correlation between the z -component of the dynamic ($\lambda_{inc} = 800$ nm) first hyperpolarizability (β_z in a.u.) and the tilt angles characterizing the orientation of the AZO units within the SAMs (θ_{AZO} , θ_{Ph1} and θ_{Ph2} , in degrees).

4.6 Effects of intermolecular electrostatic interactions

Figure S20: Distributions of the static β , β_z and a_β values of isolated molecules (*isol*) and PC-Embedded molecules (*env*) for the two isomers of AZO-A. Average values and standard deviations are also reported.

Figure S21: Distributions of the static β , β_z and a_β values of isolated molecules (*isol*) and PC-Embedded molecules (*env*) for the two isomers of AZO-D. Average values and standard deviations are also reported.

References

- (S1) Tonnelé, C.; Champagne, B.; Muccioli, L.; Castet, F. Nonlinear Optical Contrast in Azobenzene-Based Self-Assembled Monolayers. *Chemistry of Materials* **2019**, *31*, 6759–

6769.

- (S2) Cembran, A.; Bernardi, F.; Garavelli, M.; Gagliardi, L.; Orlandi, G. On the Mechanism of the cis-trans Isomerization in the Lowest Electronic States of Azobenzene: S0, S1, and T1. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **2004**, *126*, 3234–3243.